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CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

ABSTRACTS AND THESIS

Organizers of conference

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International Center for Research, Education and Training

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AZERBAIJAN-TURKEY

**THE FIRST INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC – PRACTICAL VIRTUAL
CONFERENCE SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY IN MODERN
SOCIETY: PROBLEMS, PROGNOSSES AND SOLUTIONS**

TURKEY, İZMİR SEPTEMBER 26-27, 2020

AZERBAYCAN-TÜRKİYE

**MODERN TOPLUMDA BİLİM VE TEKNOLOJİ: SORUNLAR,
TAHMINLER VE ÇÖZÜMLER BİRİNCİ ULUSLARARASI BİLİMSEL -
PRATİK VİRTÜAL KONFERANS**

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PROGRAM AT A GLANCE

First day	26 September 2020
Moderators	Ayten Gulshahin
Opening ceremony	Namig Isazade
Topics	ECONOMY / İQTİSADİYYAT / ЭКОНОМИКА / EKONOMİ
	Olga Tkachuk, Anna Levchenko, Halyna Kuzmenko The key determinants of the innovative oriented economies forming in the context of the world's countries prosperity ensuring.
	Nataliia Shalimova, Halyna Kuzmenko Taxable capacity of business entity and tax passports as an instrument for its identification and assessment.
	Yurii Malakhovskiy, Oleksandr Levchenko, Hussain Nabulsi Innovative oriented development of the social sphere of the regional ecosystem' scientific and production cluster.
	Tatiana Melnyk, Volodymyr Shalimov Specific issues and tendency of development and financing of transport sector: region aspects.
	Oksana Storozhuk, Alexey Zayarnuk Staff support for the development of the digital economy of Ukraine.
	Elena Magopets, Olga Roeva Accounting support for the formation of information about stocks in the enterprise management system.
	Mikhail Vasiliev Customs control of the import of goods: organizational forms, main stages and principles of implementation.
	Maria Fadeeva The theoretical aspects of the emotional intelligence of preschool children.
	Sədaqət İbrahimova Kimya sənayesinin idxal-ixrac məhsullarının tənzimlənməsi perspektivləri.
	Али Магомедов Влияние пандемии COVID-19 на развитие онлайн-ритейл.
	Nurlan Hacızadə Azərbaycanda enerji effektivliyinin yüksəldilməsi istiqamətləri.
	Elşən Hacızadə AZƏRBAYCANIN ELEKTROENERGETİKA SEKTORUNDA İNKİŞAFIN BAŞLICA HƏDƏFLƏRİ
	Lamara Qoqiauri Types and structural peculiarities of ecosystem.
	Khatia Udesiani Small and medium enterprises development trends and challenges in Georgia.
	Lela Kintsurashvili Peculiarities of human capital formation in Georgia.
	Loid Karchava, Ekaterine Lomia Geopolitical significance of the Anaklia deep sea port for Georgia: a new strategic hub in Eurasia
Topics	HISTORICAL AND HUMANITARIAN SCIENCES / TARİX VƏ HUMANİTAR ELMLƏR / TARİH VE İNSANİ BİLİMLER
	Tatiana Scriabina Oleg Problems of the cultural integration of the deported Crimean Tatars in 90 years xx century.

	Наталья Колосова Этапы формирования мотивации будущих педагогов к профессиональному самосовершенствованию.
	Анна Хитрова Методика преподавания дисциплины «основы вожатской деятельности» обучающимся гуманитарных специальностей.
	Мария Фадеева Особенности использования технологии педагогического проектирования в учебно-воспитательном процессе.
	Екатерина Безносюк Образовательная среда как фактор социализации личности подростков.
	Татьяна Красникова Использование активных форм проведения практических занятий при изучении дисциплины «психолого-педагогическое консультирование и коррекция в образовании» для подготовки магистров направления подготовки 44.04.02 психолого-педагогическое образование.
	Оксана Бондарь Тьюторство как технология педагогической поддержки.
Topics	AGRICULTURAL, ENVIRONMENTAL & NATURAL SCIENCES / KƏND TƏSƏRRÜFATI, ƏTRAF MÜHİT VƏ TƏBİƏT ELMLƏRİ / TARIM, ÇEVRE VE DOĞAL BİLİMLER
Second day	27 September 2020
Moderators	Ayten Gulshahin Namig Isazade
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	Sain Safarova Reparative osteogenesis in diabetes mellitus.
	Guliko Kiliptari, Grigol Nemsadze, Miranda Kokhraidze Covid-19 and massive embolism.
	Aytakin Hasanova, Nargiz Yahyazada, Goychak Gurbanbayli A case report with 6; 8 translocations.
	Giorgi Gogishvili, Shalva Petriashvili, Nino Nanobashvili, Nino Megrelishvili, Iamze Taboridze Association of blood group ab0 with coronary artery disease in young adults in Georgian population.
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	Khonsuluv Sohbnazarova, Muzaffar Muminov, Shakhlo Miralimova Anti-staphylococcal and anti-pseudomonas activity of lactobacillus plantarum mal
	Tamar Giorgadze, Sophio Giorgadze, Shalva Pharulava Effect of metal-ceramic prosthesis on gingival mucosa.

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ASSESSMENT OF MOVEMENT IN THE JOINT AFTER HIP REPLACEMENT WITH THE INCLUDING OF DEEP OSCILLATION IN POSTOPERATIVE REHABILITATION

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ABSTRACT

Background: DEEP Oscillation® (Deep Vibration) is an electromechanical procedure with deep therapy that allow to create a pulsed electrostatic field between the hand applicator and the processing better tissue nutrition, enhanced cellular metabolism, faster healing.

The purpose of this work is to evaluate the movement of the joint during the inclusion of deep oscillation method in standard therapy (complex rehabilitation) after endoprosthesis.

Methods: From January, 1st 2018 until December, 31st 2020 a total of n= 52 patients (21 men and 43 women) with a mean age of 65.4 years were enrolled in this study.

We studied patients from the Arena 2 rehabilitation center during the endoprosthetic rehabilitation period who underwent comprehensive treatment according to our scheme - the inclusion of deep vibrations in traditional treatment. Clinical data from 80 patients who were rehabilitated by traditional methods were used as control.

Both groups were treated orthopedic rehabilitation program (follow-up treatment). The Treatment spectrum included: u. a. Pain therapy procedures, strength training of the muscles that guide the hip joint, coordination exercises, including manual medical treatment techniques, Ergometer training, occupational therapy, medical training therapy and physical Therapy. In addition to the appropriate supply of aids orthopedic shoe adjustments were also made if necessary.

In experimental group the additional DEEP OSCILLATION® treatment was carried out with portable devices "DEEP OSCILLATION® PERSONAL" (Physiomed, Schnaittach /Laipersdorf, Germany) by Hand applicator. The Individual treatment lasted 18 minutes and was done once daily, in total in 15 to 20 Units performed. Here came a treatment program with the frequencies 160 Hz (8 min) and 60 Hz (10 min) for Application that had been preprogrammed on special treatment cards. The standardized treatment on operated leg was done in the direction of movement of a lymphatic drainage.

Kinesotherapy program including positional treatment of the operated leg, aiming anti-edema effect, passive and active musculoskeletal exercises and joint mobilization techniques to strengthen the muscles of the thigh and gluteal muscles, as well as to increase the volume of movement in the hip joint. Functional medical gymnastics, including sitting training and getting up from a sitting position.

Statistical analysis: The Statistical significance was defined as a p value of <0.05. Data were analyzed using the SPSS 23.

Results: There is no reliable difference between the sexes and age groups.

In the study group, the length of rehabilitation time was significantly reduced compared to the control group.

The frequency of patients with more than 90° flexions is significantly higher in the study group and the frequency of patients with 90° and less flexions is significantly lower.

The study group has a significantly higher incidence of patients with more than 30° abduction and a significantly lower incidence of those with 15° or fewer abduction; had a significantly higher incidence of patients with more than 15° adduction and a significantly lower incidence of patients with an adduction of 15° and less and had a significantly higher frequency of patients with more than 30° external rotations and a significantly lower frequency of patients with more than 30° external rotations.

Conclusion: Involvement of deep oscillation in the rehabilitation program after hip joint arthroplasty, reduces the timing of rehabilitation and increases the parameters of movement in the joint

Keywords: deep oscillation, hip arthroplasty, movement in the joint.

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REPARATIVE OSTEOGENESIS IN DIABETES MELLITUS

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ABSTRACT

This study is intended for systematic analysis aimed at assessing the correlation between markers of bone metabolism and bone mineral density in patients with diabetes mellitus, for early prediction of destructive changes in bone tissue. Clinically, remodeling markers and bone mineral density are independent predictors of bone changes. However, the results of the analysis showed that the measurement of bone remodeling markers is more informative in type 2 diabetes compared with x-ray absorptiometry.

Key words: diabetes mellitus; bone remodeling markers; osteopathy

Introduction: Osteopathy in diabetes mellitus (DM), is a serious chronic complications of this disease, refers to secondary osteoporosis, the prevalence of which is about 30-50%, is one of the promising areas of research. The study of the pathogenetic mechanisms of bone disorders in diabetes-related risk factors for osteoporosis are important in terms of the formation of risk groups and the timely implementation of preventive measures in patients with type 1 and type 2 diabetes.

Aim: To assess the effect of changes in the body of men and women with type 1 and type 2 diabetes on the state of bone mineral density and metabolic rate. Determine the direction of changes in serum markers of bone remodeling and bone mineral density of both sexes patients with this disease.

Materials and methods: 98 patients with type 1 diabetes (57 female and 41 male) and and 137 (52 men, 85 women) type 2 diabetes were included into the study. The average of patients with type 1 diabetes was 55.8 ± 0.7 years, with type 2 diabetes was 58.9 ± 1.5 years. Duration of diabetes was 16.6 ± 0.6 and $8,1 \pm 0,7$ years, BMI was 26.07 ± 0.2 and $30 \pm 0,4$ kg / m², HBA1c was $7.4 \pm 0, 2\%$ and $7.9 \pm 0,6\%$. The nondiabetic control group consisted of 82 patients (F : 48 and M : 34, mean \pm SD age 55.97 ± 0.9). Investigated the parameters of phosphorus-calcium metabolism (Ca²⁺, P), calcitrop hormones level: 25 (OH)D₃, PTH, Calcitonin, level of bone formation markers: alkaline phosphatase (ALP), aminoterminal propeptide of procollagen type I (PINP) and bone resorption marker - C-terminal telopeptide (b-CTx) by the immune-enzyme analysis method. The bone mineral density (BMD) measured by DXA absorptiometry at the lumbar spine (L1-L4), proximal femur and femoral neck area.

Statistical analyses were performed with standard software package "BioStat Pro 6.2.2.0". For all analyses, a two-sided *p*-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: The results of the study demonstrated that the content of serum bone remodeling markers in patients with T1DM and T2DM, in comparison to the control group, indicate pathological processes in bone remodeling with decrease bone formation marker *PINP* in patients with T1DM by 16%, with T2DM by 12% in comparison with the control and an increase bone resorption marker *b-CTx* by 32% with T1DM and in 25% patients with T2DM, of whom of women were 1,5 times more than men. Patients with T2DM had lower *b-CTx* values and a relatively higher level of *P1NP*, which reflects a less pronounced change in bone turnover compared to patients with T1DM, regardless of age and duration of disease. *T*-score BMD of L1–L4 area was reduced in 64 and 44% of patients with T1DM and T2DM; *T*-score BMD of femoral neck area— in 41 and 36% of patients (Fig.1).

Figure 1. BMD assessment at the T-SD L1-L4, PFA and FN area in patients with type 1 diabetes, type 2 diabetes and a control group

Discussion: The data showed that the lowest T-score was found in female in the lumbar spine and in the left hip, accounting for a total of 42% and 13% of the total number of patients with DM .

Observed low bone mineral density in patients with diabetes is associated with an increased bone resorption. The level of bone resorption marker b-CTx in patients with diabetes was higher in comparison with control group. Moreover, in male with T1DM, a statistically significant increase in the level of b-CTx ($p < 0.05$) was observed in comparison with the control group. In T2DM, disorders of bone remodeling processes was accompanied by less significant changes in BMD.

Conclusion: The results of T-score studying, confirmed that in both men and women with diabetes, in comparison with the control, the bone density in the vertebrae was reduced. The level of b-CTx showed a statistically significant negative correlation with the BMD of the lumbar spine, consisting mainly of a spongy bone with high metabolic activity. This indicates that both bones metabolism markers and DXA can be considered as independent indicators of changes in bone tissue, which can be of great importance for early diagnosis and evaluation of the effectiveness of the therapy.

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THE KEY DETERMINANTS OF THE INNOVATIVE ORIENTED ECONOMIES FORMING IN THE CONTEXT OF THE WORLD'S COUNTRIES PROSPERITY ENSURING

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SUMMARY

The paper is devoted to the evaluation the impact of key determinants of innovation development and ensuring the worlds' countries prosperity and working out the ways of increasing the innovative economic growth. By using the international statistic data of 40-ty countries, there were analyzed such indicators, as the level of GDP per capita and other indicators, such as expenditure on education, tertiary enrolment, graduates in science & engineering, number of researchers, gross expenditure on R&D, knowledge-intensive employment, intellectual property payments, high-tech imports, high-tech net exports and creative goods exports. As a result of calculating pairwise correlation coefficients between indicators, it was determined, that the most significant influence on the level of GDP per capita make such three variables: number of researchers, gross expenditure on R&D, knowledge-intensive employment. There were suggested the main directions of innovative development and prosperity raising for four groups of actors within the Quadruple Helix Model: state (government), universities and scientific institutions, business, civil society.

Keywords: innovation, prosperity, human resources, research activity, education, expenditure, knowledge, high-tech technology, creativity

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TAXABLE CAPACITY OF BUSINESS ENTITY AND TAX PASSPORTS AS AN INSTRUMENT FOR ITS IDENTIFICATION AND ASSESSMENT

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ABSTRACT

A precondition for a successful budgetary and fiscal policy is to increase the revenue of the budget system by expanding tax capacity of the economy which implies the need to stimulate the growth of tax capacity and create a reliable information base support for its assessment. However there are significant problems related to a timely strategic and, especially, operational decisions to obtain information of the required amount and quality. The concept of determining the economic essence of the notion of "taxable capacity of a business entity" and its elements is proposed, within which the classification criteria (optimal and actual taxable capacity), the structure (resource and structural approach), functions (resource-saving, regulatory, informational and analytical), the place and role in the system of tax administration are distinguished. Using of this concept ensure the correct identification of the entity from the standpoint of its capacities to provide tax obligations to the state were outlined. The principles of forming tax passports of different business entities are laid out. The priority descriptions of key aspects of activity of different entities which allow estimating their tax potential and increasing tax incomes to the budgets have been highlighted. Taking into account the significant analytical orientation of tax passports it is proposed to include the following key indicators describing the entity, grouped into three groups: group I includes indicators that characterize the financial status of the entity; group II includes indicators that characterize the tax burden of the enterprise; group III includes indicators that characterize the tax culture of the subject and the effectiveness of the state financial control bodies, in the first place, the tax authorities. Qualitative compilation of tax passports with application of other documents on tax administration will help to determine real tax burden of a particular business entity and develop directions for its optimization, conduct rational tax policy, ensure the necessary amount of tax revenues to the state and local budget system.

Keywords: capacity, taxes, taxable capacity, taxable capacity of a business entity, information support, tax passport

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INNOVATIVE ORIENTED DEVELOPMENT OF THE SOCIAL SPHERE OF THE REGIONAL ECOSYSTEM' SCIENTIFIC AND PRODUCTION CLUSTER

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the publication is to determine the prospects of innovatively oriented development of the social sphere of scientific and production clusters of regional ecosystems with the preferential use of public-private partnership tools. It is concluded that the modern method of managing the development of the social sphere is the state innovation regulation of public management of public-private partnership with the use of e-Government facilities; management of virtual networks; fundraising; outsourcing; creation of social technology platforms; crowdfunding; meeting the needs of stakeholders in obtaining high-tech social services; the formation of educational production clusters, "nodes" of stabilization and development, technical, intellectual, information, social "centers of excellence"; top-priority designing on the periphery of forward-looking, innovative and technology-intensive technologies.

Keywords: innovation; innovative oriented development; social sphere; scientific and production cluster; regional ecosystem; public-private partnership

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SPECIFIC ISSUES AND TENDENCY OF DEVELOPMENT AND FINANCING OF TRANSPORT SECTOR: REGION ASPECTS

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ABSTRACT

The transport complex belongs to the strategically important element of regional development, which includes both providing expanded access to public services for the population of remote areas, realizing the tourist potential, and strengthening industrial ties. The purpose of this article is to identify problems and growth areas of the transport sector in the region through the example of the Kirovograd's one. The tendency of priority development of land transport in the Kirovograd region, specifically automobile, has been confirmed. The key factors which influence on the transport services market development in Ukraine are given, for instance the unsatisfactory technical condition of transport, reduction of traffic during the COVID-19 pandemic, etc. The main problematic aspects of development of the transport complex in the Kirovograd region are substantiated. The main priorities for the development of transport infrastructure in the Kirovograd region are presented. In order to reduce abusive activity in the transport service market the funds transfer network implementation has been suggested. The possibility of using finance lease as a source of funding automotive maintenance during economic crisis is substantiated.

Keywords: transport, automobile, land transport, finance lease, auto financing

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ANTI-STAPHYLOCOCCAL AND ANTI-PSEUDOMONAS ACTIVITY OF LACTOBACILLUS PLANTARUM MAL

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ABSTRACT

Lactobacillus plantarum Mal strain was screened against clinical isolates of 10 Staphylococcus aureus and 5 Pseudomonas aeruginosa that had isolated from patients diagnosed with Atopic dermatitis and Phlegmon. Antibiotic resistance of the isolates was checked against dozen widely used antibiotics in dermatology representing different classes and subsequently, Lactobacillus plantarum Mal was subjected for the antagonistic activity against the clinical isolates. Lactobacillus plantarum Mal strain showed antagonistic activity against all the isolates of Staphylococcus aureus and Pseudomonas aeruginosa with average inhibition zone of 27.95 mm and 28.22 mm, respectively.

The research results suggest that the strain could be very promising for targeting antibiotic resistant bacteria strains.

Keywords: Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Staphylococcus aureus, Lactic acid bacteria, Lactobacillus, antibiotics

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КАДРОВОЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ РАЗВИТИЯ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ УКРАИНЫ

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РЕЗЮМЕ

В статье изучено состояние кадрового обеспечения ускоренного развития цифровой трансформации экономики Украины. Авторы рассматривают высококвалифицированные кадры как основу инновационных прорывов, связанных с высокими технологиями. Сделан вывод, что успешное цифровое преобразование экономической системы является базой конкурентоспособности экономики страны в глобализованном мире. Проведена оценка места Украины в развитии цифровой экономики в сравнении со странами бывшего СССР и странами-мировыми лидерами. Проведен анализ количественных и качественных показателей системы подготовки высококвалифицированных кадров в области информационных и цифровых технологий. Предложены пути обеспечения соответствия подготовки высококвалифицированных кадров требованиям цифровой экономики.

Ключевые слова: высококвалифицированные кадры, цифровая экономика, трансформация, информационно-коммуникационные технологии

STAFF SUPPORT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY OF UKRAINE

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the state of staffing for the accelerated development of the digital transformation of the Ukrainian economy. The authors consider highly qualified personnel as the basis for innovative breakthroughs associated with high technologies. It is concluded that the successful digital transformation of the economic system is the basis for the competitiveness of the country's economy in the globalized world. The place of Ukraine in the development of the digital economy was assessed in comparison with the countries of the former USSR and world leaders. The analysis of quantitative and qualitative indicators of the system for training highly qualified personnel in the field of information and digital technologies. The ways of ensuring compliance of the training of highly qualified personnel with the requirements of the digital economy are proposed.

Keywords: highly qualified personnel, digital economy, transformation, information and communication technologies

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УЧЕТНОЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ИНФОРМАЦИИ О ЗАПАСАХ В СИСТЕМЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЕМ

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РЕЗЮМЕ

В статье освещаются вопросы организации учетного процесса запасов с позиции обеспечения системы управления предприятием необходимой информацией для принятия управленческих решений. Раскрыты подходы к организации учетного процесса запасов на основе модели формирования учетной политики. Предложено авторское определение учетной политики в части учетного процесса запасов, которая рассматривается как совокупность принципов, методов и процедур, используемых предприятием для формирования качественной, достоверной, понятной и полной информации о запасах, достаточной для принятия управленческих решений и раскрытия такой информации в финансовой отчетности.

Акцентировано внимание на стоимостных критериях оценки запасов. Изложены подходы к формированию и раскрытию методов оценки, учета и процедур (элементов) учетной политики запасов. Определены вариативные элементы учетной политики запасов, обосновано их влияние на обеспечение системы управления предприятием эффективной, объективной, достоверной и своевременной информацией о запасах. **Ключевые слова:** запасы, учетная политика, учетный процесс, бухгалтерский учет, информационное обеспечение, система управления.

ACCOUNTING SUPPORT FOR THE FORMATION OF INFORMATION ABOUT STOCKS IN THE ENTERPRISE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The article highlights the issues of organizing the accounting process of stocks from the standpoint of providing the enterprise management system with the necessary information for making management decisions. The approaches to the organization of the accounting process of reserves based on the model of the formation of accounting policies are disclosed. The author's definition of the accounting policy in terms of the accounting process for inventories is proposed, which is considered as a set of principles, methods and procedures used by the enterprise to generate high-quality, reliable, understandable and complete information about inventories, sufficient for making management decisions and disclosing such information in financial statements.

Attention is focused on cost criteria for assessing reserves. The approaches to the formation and disclosure of valuation methods, accounting and procedures (elements) of the accounting policy for reserves. The variable elements of the accounting policy of reserves are determined, their influence on the provision of the enterprise management system with effective, objective, reliable and timely information about the reserves is substantiated.

Keywords: stocks, accounting policy, accounting process, accounting, information support, management system.

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ТАМОЖЕННЫЙ КОНТРОЛЬ ИМПОРТА ТОВАРОВ: ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННЫЕ ФОРМЫ, ОСНОВНЫЕ ЭТАПЫ И ПРИНЦИПЫ ОСУЩЕСТВЛЕНИЯ

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РЕЗЮМЕ

В статье проанализированы требования действующего законодательства о порядке осуществления таможенного контроля. Рассмотрено нормативно-правовое определение понятия таможенного контроля и приведен сравнительный анализ подходов к его определению в работах современных отечественных научных деятелей. Изучены особенности и порядок осуществления таможенного контроля при ввозе товаров на территорию Украины и размещение их под таможенным режимом «импорт». Предложено группирование основных принципов таможенного контроля в соответствии с его сутью. Очерчен перечень проблем, препятствующих повышению эффективности таможенного контроля.

Ключевые слова: внешнеэкономическая деятельность, импорт, таможенный контроль, таможенная декларация.

CUSTOMS CONTROL OF THE IMPORT OF GOODS: ORGANIZATIONAL FORMS, MAIN STAGES AND PRINCIPLES OF IMPLEMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the requirements of the current legislation on the procedure for the implementation of customs control. The article considers the regulatory and legal definition of the concept of customs control and provides a comparative analysis of approaches to its definition in the works of modern domestic scientists. The features and procedure for the implementation of customs control when importing goods into the territory of Ukraine and their placement under the "import" customs regime have been studied. The grouping of the basic principles of customs control in accordance with its essence is proposed. A list of problems hindering the improvement of the efficiency of customs control is outlined.

Keywords: foreign economic activity, import, customs control, customs declaration.

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THE THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF THE EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

Based on the analysis of scientific literature, the features of the development of emotional intelligence of preschool children are considered, the concept of "emotional intelligence of preschool children" is clarified.

Keywords: preschool children, emotional development, emotional intelligence.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM: In the modern society, the problem of the competence in understanding and expressing emotions is quite acute. Experts from the world economic forum in 2018 in Davos (Switzerland) listed emotional intelligence in the top of 10 most important skills in 2020. This competence was absent from the previous similar list, and this innovation is not accidental: understanding emotions and managing them are extremely important in social interaction and in the professional activity of any person.

THE MAIN MATERIAL RESEARCH: Since emotional intelligence is important for personal development, special attention should be paid to its formation and development in preschool children. At preschool age, the child's personality begins to form. At the same time, this process is closely interrelated with the development of the emotional sphere, with the formation of behavioral motives and interests, which is determined by the social environment, especially the typical relationships with adults at this stage of development [37].

A.V. Zaporozhets, noted the importance of studying of the emotional sphere of preschool children, in particular the emotional relationships of children. The scientist argued that "the education of feelings from the first years of life is an important task, because how knowledge and skills will be acquired depends crucially on the emotional attitude of the subject to the people who surround him, and the environment" [32, c. 97].

The famous psychologist Y. B. Gippenreiter, emphasizing the importance of emotions in childhood, emphasized that: "the mental organization of childhood is exceptionally beautiful, and this beauty and grace of childhood is due to the immediacy, the root of which lies in the predominant development of the emotional sphere. The younger the child is, the less objective significance the world around them acquires. It stands before him as his own emotions show. A child loves his mother and father not for their beauty, courage, but for their caring attitude, love, and warmth" [12, p. 45].

According to the psychologists (Y. V. Bratchikova, N. S. Voloshina [5], E.D. Giniyatullina [11], O. A. Putilova [31]), preschool age is characterized by rapid development of the emotional sphere, which affects children's mastery of various activities and personal development of the child.

CONCLUSIONS

The specific features of the emotional development in the preschool years are: the development of social forms of expression of emotions and feelings; the changing role of emotions in activities, the formation of emotional care; the formation of the higher feelings, – moral, intellectual, aesthetic; the ability to anticipate emotional outcomes of its activities; the transformation of the preschooler in the subject of emotional relationships, empathy for other people.

Based on the theoretical analysis, "emotional intelligence of preschool children" is understood as a stable child's ability to distinguish between emotional states (their own and those of their interlocutors), indicators of which are: the brightness of the child's expression of emotions, the ability to experience positive and negative emotions of the interlocutor (regardless of gender and age), the child's ability to empathy (the presence of empathic sensitivity), the child's ability to recognize their own positive and negative emotions, analyze them, to draw insights and actions for a variety of everyday situations. This demonstrates the close relationship between the development of human emotions and their intelligence, therefore, we can say that emotional development is the basis, one of the determining factors in the formation of emotional intelligence of a person.

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KİMYA SƏNAYESİNİN İDXAL-İXRAC MƏHSULLARININ TƏNZİMLƏNMƏSİ PERSPEKTİVLƏRİ

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XÜLASƏ

Kimya sənayesi dünya iqtisadiyyatına təsir edən bütün inkişafı əhəmiyyətli sahədir. Qlobal böyümə dünyadakı dəyişikliklər xammal qiymətlərinin dəyişkənliyinə səbəb olsa da, tələbin dəyişməsi kimya sənayesindəki məhsul istehsalını artırmaqda davam edir. Bu dinamika ilə dünya kimya sənayesinin ortamüddətli perspektivdə qlobal iqtisadiyyatda sürətlə inkişafı gözlənilir. Sənayedə güclü rəqabət, ətraf mühitin tənzimlənməsi və qlobal ticarətdə qoruyucu meyllər sektorun əsas tərəfləridir.

Uzunmüddətli perspektivdə Cənubi Qafqaz regionunda dəyər zəncirinin ən yüksək segmentində fəaliyyət göstərən müəssisələr Azərbaycan Respublikasıdır. Bu məqsədlə xarici sərmayələrin dəstəklənməsi, bu sahədə fəaliyyət göstərən müəssisələrə maliyyə və texnoloji dəstək verilməsi kimi siyasət davam etməkdədir.

Müəssisələrin müasir texnologiyalar əsasında yenidən qurulması, onların modernləşdirilməsi və avtomatlaşdırılması, yerli ehtiyat və xammal ilə yeni sənaye komplekslərinin yaradılması, ixrac yönümlü məhsulların istehsalı və genişləndirilməsi, rəqabətli sənaye istehsalının qurulmasıdır. İxrac yönümlü istehsal sahələrinin yaradılması və yüksək ixtisaslı kadr potensialının hazırlanması ilə kimya sənaye məhsullarının idxaldan asılılığı əhəmiyyətli dərəcədə azaldılacaq və orta tələbat sahələri yerli məhsullarla qarşılanacaqdır.

Açar sözlər: kimya sənayesi, qlobal iqtisadiyyat, qlobal ticarət, ixrac yönümlü məhsullar, sənaye aktivləri, regional bazarlar, beynəlxalq bazarlar, qiymətli məhsullar segmenti, texnoloji məhsul.

PROSPECTS FOR THE REGULATION OF IMPORT-EXPORT PRODUCTS OF THE CHEMICAL INDUSTRY

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SUMMARY

The chemical industry is the most sensitive to all developments affecting the world economy. Although global growth and changes in the world have led to volatility in commodity prices, changes in demand continue to increase production in the chemical industry. With these dynamics, the world chemical industry is expected to develop rapidly in the global economy in the medium term. Strong competition in industry, environmental regulation and protective trends in global trade are key aspects of the sector.

In the long run, the enterprises operating in the highest segment of the value chain in the South Caucasus region are in the Republic of Azerbaijan. To this end, policies such as supporting foreign investment and providing financial and technological support to enterprises operating in this field continue.

Reconstruction of enterprises on the basis of modern technologies, their modernization and automation, creation of new industrial complexes with local resources and raw materials, production and expansion of export-oriented products, establishment of competitive industrial production. With the creation of export-oriented industries and the training of highly qualified human resources, the dependence of the chemical industry on imports will be significantly reduced, and areas of average demand will be met by local products.

Keywords: chemical industry, global economy, global trade, export-oriented products, industrial assets, regional markets, international markets, valuable product segment, technological product

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EFFECT OF METAL-CERAMIC PROSTHESIS ON GINGIVAL MUCOSA

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ABSTRACT

The fixed dental prosthesis is one of the most commonly used prosthesis in dental clinical practice for restoring function and health of oral tissues. This type of dental prosthesis is not without complications, as these restorations often extend into the gingival sulcus, and gingival epithelial cells come into contact with them. Unfortunately, they also alter and modify oral microbial flora. The aim of the present study is to identify the dynamics of changes of mucosa in the region of metallo-ceramic prosthesis. We have examined three groups of patients, according to the length of wearing time of metallo-ceramic prosthesis: I group - 1year, II group – 1-5 years and III group – 6-10 years. Each group includes two subgroup, where was studied influence of supportive and intermediate parts of Metal-Ceramic prosthesis on gingival mucosa. The gingival mucosa was examined by Papanicolaou staining and cytomorphometric indexes. A review of the literature and the results of our study demonstrated the effect of metallo-ceramic prosthesis on the dynamics of changes in the surrounding gingival mucosa. At the same time, the literature searches around the present study also showed possible reasons for the changes mentioned above. It was shown that the success of fixed dental prosthesis depends on many factors which should be considered during treatment planning. Therefore, a detailed analysis of the changes in the gingival mucosa surrounding the fixed ceramic-metal prosthesis and their possible causes are necessary prerequisites for successful prosthetics.

Keywords: Fixed Metal-Ceramic prosthesis; Gingival Mucosa; Cytomorphometric Indexes;

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COVID-19 AND MASSIVE EMBOLISM

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ABSTRACT

Objective : Hospitalized patients with COVID-19 were characterized by a high rate of thromboembolic complications and in hospital mortality.

The exact mechanisms of COVID-19 induced thrombosis have not been elucidated.

The early pathogenesis in COVID-19 (Huertas *et al.*) pneumonia defined by a widespread endotheliitis affecting multiple organ systems, viral inclusion are observed within endothelial cells accompanied by apoptosis, inflammatory cell infiltration and microvascular thrombosis.

The primary infection initiates alveolar injury and the resulting inflammatory response, including production of inflammatory cytokines, including IL-6, as well as activation and recruitment of mononuclear cells and neutrophils causing more tissue damage, including damage to the capillary endothelium. In addition to the procoagulant effectors derived as the result of inflammation the usual thrombo-protective state of the vascular endothelial cells is disrupted; Both pathophysiologic changes lead to the development of microvascular thrombosis. Over time the pathology of ARDS progresses to a proliferative and then a fibrotic state, which is fatal.

We presented one case when the patient developed severe respiratory failure after massive pulmonary embolism and coma after ischemic stroke. Patient had many comorbidities with COPD, heart failure (HFrEF) and diabetes mellitus.

Conclusion: High values of d-dimer could be related to a higher activation of blood coagulation in COVID-19 patients secondary to a systemic inflammatory response syndrome – or as a direct consequence of the SARS-CoV-2 itself. Pulmonary thrombosis was the confluence of processes, endothelial inflammation with no evidence of DVT. Tissue factor, up-regulated on platelets, leucocytes during inflammation, leading to activation coagulation pathways and promote the formation of fibrin. The profound hypoxaemia is a likely driver of vasoconstriction, inflammation and thrombosis. The origin of Covid-19-associated pulmonary emboli and lung microcirculatory thrombotic disease: Interaction of inflammation and coagulation

Keywords: Thrombosis, Pulmonary embolism, inflammation.

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ВЛИЯНИЕ ПАНДЕМИИ COVID-19 НА РАЗВИТИЕ ОНЛАЙН-РИТЕЙЛ

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РЕЗЮМЕ

Статья посвящена изучению проблем и перспектив развития онлайн торговли в условиях коронавирусной пандемии, определению факторов и тенденций развития дистанционной торговли, выявлению путей эффективного функционирования интернет-магазинов на основе применения современных стратегий цифрового маркетинга. Пандемия COVID-19 переформатировала деятельность общества и бизнеса, высветила актуальность цифровизации экономики и насущную необходимость преодоления цифрового разрыва России от стран-лидеров, а также цифрового неравенства между регионами и секторами экономики, вынудила перейти ритейлеров в условиях самоизоляции населения на дистанционные формы торговли. Покупатели достаточно быстро адаптировались к онлайн-шопингу и сформировалась новая устойчивая покупательская привычка – покупка товаров и Интернете. Этот потребительский опыт (customer experience) должен стать в перспективе пятым «Р» маркетингового микса. В целях устранения цифрового неравенства и развития инфраструктуры дистанционной торговли предложено резко увеличить затраты на информационно-коммуникационные технологии в депрессивных регионах. Государству следует создавать благоприятную институциональную среду развития электронного бизнеса, устранить пробелы в его нормативном регулировании, повысить доверие к интернет-магазинам.

Ключевые слова: пандемия, онлайн-торговля, интернет-магазин: продвижение сайта; маркетинговые стратегии

INFLUENCE OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF ONLINE RETAIL

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to studying the problems and prospects for the development of online commerce in the context of the coronavirus pandemic, identifying factors and trends in the development of distance selling, identifying ways to effectively operate online stores based on the use of modern digital marketing strategies. The COVID-19 pandemic has reformatted the activities of society and business, highlighted the relevance of digitalization of the economy and the urgent need to bridge the digital divide of Russia from the leading countries, as well as the digital inequality between regions and sectors of the economy, forced retailers to switch to remote forms in conditions of self-isolation of the population trade. Customers quickly adapted to online shopping and a new sustainable buying habit was formed - buying goods on the Internet. This customer experience should be the fifth "P" of the marketing mix in the long run. In order to eliminate the digital inequality and develop the infrastructure of remote trade, it is proposed to dramatically increase the cost of information and communication technologies in depressed regions. The state should create a favorable institutional environment for the development of e-business, eliminate gaps in its regulatory regulation, and increase trust in online stores.

Keywords: pandemic, online trade, online store: website promotion; marketing strategies

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TYPES AND STRUCTURAL PECULIARITIES OF ECOSYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The work explores the different types of innovation ecosystems based on the territorial principle. The whole world innovation ecosystem, national innovation ecosystems, regional, as well as, local innovation ecosystems (Technopolymer) corporate, industrial and innovative individuals' ecosystems are characterized in this work. The article highlights important elements of innovation ecosystem such as industry, supportive infrastructure entrepreneurship, scientific field and venture investment market. The basic model of the interaction of innovation ecosystem entities is interesting, in which are represented the main relationships between innovation ecosystem entities.

Keyword: Industry, Venture Investment Market, Scientific Field, Venture Funds, Startups, Business Angels, Technoparks, the World Innovation ecosystem, National Innovation ecosystem, Local Innovation ecosystem.

INTRODUCTION

During recent years certain positive changes have been introduced in our country. The Government recognizes state innovative development in the innovative policy of the country to be one of the preferable tasks, which have been improved through modest practical activities. State-private partnership programs have been developed in the field of finances and infrastructure, technoparks and business-incubators have been opened, startup program is being developed widely and successfully, etc.

Innovation ecosystem is the complex interrelated system of different form of ownership, organizations, state institutions, legal agencies, social relations, services and practitioners. Innovators, innovative individuals or the persons creating, and distributing innovations, based on their own motivation or/and requirements make grounds to the innovation ecosystem. Theoretical problems of the above issues require studying of the significant elements of innovation ecosystem, as well as types of the ecosystem, per different signs of classification.

CONCLUSION

Classification of innovation ecosystems is presented in the work, according to the different signs, along with the significant elements of the innovation ecosystem, which is important issue of classification of the innovation system. Study of all considered types of ecosystem: global, national, regional, local, corporate, industrial and innovation individuals allows scientific evaluation of their theoretical and practical importance, to determine performance and direction of each of them.

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SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES DEVELOPMENT TRENDS AND CHALLENGES IN GEORGIA

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Introduction. Developing countries in the modern world have many challenges, between them - Georgia. One of the main challenges is the development of small and medium enterprises. Although several reforms have been implemented in Georgia in recent years, such as: creating a conducive environment for business development, reducing the tax burden, limitation of various artificial barriers and more, small and medium enterprises have some problems.

The article discusses the trends of product launches by small and medium enterprises since 2015, the share of their output in total output, number of employees by enterprise size categories. The article analyzes the measures taken by the government in this direction.

Aim and tasks. The purpose of the research is to study and analyze the trends and challenges of small and medium enterprises development in Georgia, the generalization of existing state support and justification of objective necessity, develop practical recommendations.

Results. The article discusses the current state of development of small and medium enterprises in Georgia, its contribution to the improvement of the socio-economic situation in the country and the objective necessity of state support.

Conclusions. In recent years, as a result of reforms in Georgia, the country's investment and business environment have improved significantly - administrative barriers have been significantly reduced and public services improved. However, some measures are needed to support the development of small and medium enterprises, namely, it is necessary to increase the competitiveness of the private sector, improve the investment and business environment, political stability, strengthen property rights, support state production, increase access to finance, develop innovation and technology.

Keywords: Small and Medium Enterprises, Reforms, Produce in Georgia, Products, Number of Employees.

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PECULIARITIES OF HUMAN CAPITAL FORMATION IN GEORGIA

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ABSTRACT

Under the globalization of economic systems and resource constraints, investing in human capital is determined as a system of measures aimed at increasing the labor productivity of workers, the most important of which is investing in education. As international experience confirms, an educated and skilled workforce can perform better and more difficult work.

In this regard recently a number of reforms implemented in the Georgian education system, however according to statistics, the results achieved are significantly lower than similar education indicators in developed countries. Its development requires an analysis of the ongoing processes in the education system and an increase of state control, that will reduce the risk of making possible mistakes and make the management of the education system more efficient. Mental and physical abilities, innate skills and acquired habits, knowledge and experience of a human can be considered as human capital if they are using effective and profitable.

The efficiency of human capital can be increased by spending on education, vocational training, health care, etc. of which spending on education is particularly important.

As experience has shown, investing in human capital has a positive effect on human economic activity and revenue growth. It is much easier for a knowledgeable person to master new technologies and adapt to current social changes. The article discusses the essence and evolution of a theory of human capital and the peculiarities of the formation of human capital in Georgia.

According to the research, the number of students in each academic year greatly varies by program. In process of choosing a speciality, most entrants have neither its own sphere of interest nor the demands of the labor market have been understood, which leads to misallocation of human capital and inefficient spending of the budget.

Differentiation is also observed in the gender perspective. If the number of boys among students enrolled in the 2000s exceeded the number of girls, in recent years this trend changed in the opposite direction. Among the graduates, boys have advantage over girls too.

Although expenditures on human capital development have been growing in Georgia in recent years and the education system is being actively reformed but education rating of Georgia is still low compared to other countries. This indicates the need to revise the reforms.

Keywords: Capital, Human capital, Education.

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ПРОБЛЕМЫ КУЛЬТУРНОЙ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ ДЕПОРТИРОВАННЫХ КРЫМСКИХ ТАТАР В 90-Х ГГ. XX В.

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РЕЗЮМЕ

В статье рассмотрены проблемы культурной интеграции депортированных крымских татар в 90-х гг. XX в. Деятельность государственных органов власти АР Крым связанных с проблемами репатриантов, крымскотатарской культурой и образованием.

Ключевые слова: интеграция, политика, культура, образование, возрождение, крымские татары.

РЕЗЮМЕ

У статті розглянуто проблеми культурної інтеграції депортованих кримських татар у 90-х рр. XX ст. Діяльність державних органів влади АР Крим пов'язаних з проблемами репатріантів, кримськотатарською культурою та освітою.

Ключові слова: інтеграція, політика, культура, освіта, відродження, кримські татари.

ABSTRACT

The article deals with the problems of cultural integration of deported Crimean Tatars in the 90s of the XX century. Activities of the state authorities of the Republic of Crimea related to the problems of repatriates, Crimean Tatar culture and education.

Keywords: integration, politics, culture, education, the revival of the Crimean Tatars.

PROBLEMS OF THE CULTURAL INTEGRATION OF THE DEPORTED CRIMEAN TATARS IN THE 90S. XX CENTURY

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the problems of cultural integration of deported Crimean Tatars in the 90s of the XX century. Activities of the state authorities of the Republic of Crimea related to the problems of repatriates, Crimean Tatar culture and education.

Thus, during the return and settlement of the Crimean Tatars in the 1990s. the central state and executive authorities made efforts to create a legal framework and conditions for the provision and implementation of policies aimed at supporting and developing education in the native language, culture and art of repatriates. Concrete long-term measures were taken to finance and provide material support for the education system, cultural institutions, creative teams, associations and unions. State policy gradually found understanding and support among the Crimean Tatar population, public and international organizations. At the same time, negative points should be noted. Some of the decisions taken were ill-conceived and subsequently unfulfilled. The activities of the authorities in the ARC in meeting the pressing problems of the Crimean Tatars were aimed at solving urgent issues and did not have a long-term program aimed at regional cultural integration.

Keywords: integration, politics, culture, education, the revival of the Crimean Tatars.

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A CASE REPORT WITH 6; 8 TRANSLOCATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Proband is a 30-year-old woman. He was married to a 33-year-old healthy man for 6 years and was sent to our center for cytogenetic research due to recurrent miscarriage. There is no kinship between parents. Our case has no surviving children with a reproductive history including 3 miscarriages (2 months old) and a 6-week intrauterine death. One of the miscarriages occurred as a result of pregnancy provided by IVF. The proband is a total of 6 siblings, 3 girls and 3 boys. The siblings are all married and no one has a miscarriage. There is no miscarriage story in the mother of the proband. Physical examination of the proband is normal, but ultrasound examination revealed that kidney localizations are different from each other.

Standard cytogenetic methods were used for karyotype analysis of the proband and her partner. A 72-hour culture was performed using phytohemagglutinin (PHA) -induced peripheral blood lymphocytes. The metaphase preparations obtained after the culture were stained with GTG banding method and chromosomes in 30-50 metaphase plates were evaluated in terms of numerical and structural irregularities. As a result of the chromosome analysis of the case, 46, XX, t (6; 8) (6q 25-27; 8q 23) karyotype was determined. His wife's karyotype was determined as normal (46, XY). Chromosome analysis could not be performed because the proband's parents and siblings were far away.

In this study, during the genetic counseling process, the family was informed about balanced reciprocal translocation carriage, the possibilities of their next pregnancy, PGD and prenatal diagnosis for their next pregnancy. The family is considering PGD application and is followed up during the genetic counseling process.

Keywords: Recurrent Abortions, Fetal Wastage, Reciprocal Translocation.

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ASSOCIATION OF BLOOD GROUP AB0 WITH CORONARY ARTERY DISEASE IN YOUNG ADULTS IN GEORGIAN POPULATION

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ABSTRACT

OBJECTIVE: Several reports have suggested that ABO blood group system is associated with the risk of CAD.

Aim: establish the association of blood group AB0 with CAD in young adults in Georgian population.

METHODS: Under our observation were 107 patients with ischemic heart disease, aged 18-45 years, From the St. John The Merciful Private Clinic contingent. Examination: anamnesis, cardiography, echocardiography, coronography, blood lipid metabolism.

We used the distribution of blood groups in the general population of Georgia as a control

The differences between the frequency of ABO blood groups in CAD patients and healthy blood donors were tested using χ^2 -test.

RESULTS: We studied the role of genetic predisposition in the development of cardiovascular disease in the Georgian population under 45 years of age. In 19 (21.6%) patients, early detection of ischemic heart disease (under 45 years of age) CVD was observed in first degree relatives.

Blood group 0 shows significantly associations with the early development of cardiovascular disease, frequency 0 antigen in CAD group - 74.77%, in population - 50.86%($p<0.0001$).

In case of group 0, the incidence of dyslipidemia is significantly high, then in group with A antigen – Respectively 38(46.91%) and 5(20.83), $p=0.0224$. In the case of group 0, compared to group A, significantly increased: the mass index -32.05 ± 5.44 and 29.38 ± 4.20 $p=0.0140$ respectively, Tchol - 5.24 ± 1.30 and 4.62 ± 1.00 , $p=0.0180$ and TG - 2.84 ± 1.57 and 1.83 ± 0.70 , $p=0.0029$, the mean LDL is significantly low - 1.27 ± 0.48 and 1.20 ± 0.28 , $p=0.3602$.

The 10-year risk is significantly higher in patients with blood type 0 4.46 ± 3.15 , than in group A - 2.42 ± 2.45 , $p=0.0044$

CONCLUSIONS: blood group 0 increased risk fatal cardiovascular disease in young Georgian population;

Study of blood groups during coronary heart disease will help to clarify the prognostic factors of the disease and reduce the global burden of cardiovascular disease.

Keywords: AB0, risk factors CAD, dyslipidemia.

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PRE-IMPLANTATION GENETIC DIAGNOSIS

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Pre-implantation Genetic Diagnosis (PGD) is the diagnosis of genetic disorders in human embryos prior to implantation into the endometrium, i.e. before the phase of transfer on the program of in vitro fertilization (IVF). A biopsy of one blastomer in an embryo that is at the cleavage stage (6-10 blastomeres) or a biopsy of the trophoctoderm (the outer layer of cells) at the blastocyst stage (day 5 of embryo development) is typically performed for analysis. The main advantage of PGD is that there is no selective termination of pregnancy when it is used and the chance of giving birth to a child without any diagnosed genetic diseases is quite high. There are discrepant data in literature on the effectiveness of PGD as part of the program of assisted reproductive technologies (ART).

According to some studies including ASRM (American Society for Reproductive Medicine) data, application of PGD doesn't increase the frequency of pregnancies with in vitro fertilization (IVF). This may be due to imperfection of the technique of the blastomer sampling procedure or the choice of a laboratory screening method to diagnose aneuploidy and microstructural chromosomal abnormalities simultaneously in all chromosomes. The method of array comparative genomichybridization (CGH) showed high performance for clinical studies on embryo transfer within ART (69-70%). While there is the high genetic abnormalities detection rate in PGD based on many studies, the frequency of pregnancies with this method doesn't exceed 30-40%.

Study of the structure of embryo chromosomal disorders based on pre-implantation genetic diagnosis in the program of assisted reproductive technology as well as the impact of this procedure on the results of pregnancies is, therefore, of particular interest.

We studied chromosomal abnormalities of embryos in 86 females with different IVF outcomes. Pre-implantation study of the embryos was conducted by the FISH method in 42 females with positive IVF outcomes and in 44 females with negative IVF outcomes. The quality of the embryos was assessed on the third day of culture.

In summary, the study of pre-implantation embryo characteristics in the IVF program revealed higher indices for embryos without chromosomal abnormalities in the group with positive IVF outcomes and lower indices for the relative frequency of embryos with chromosomal abnormalities as against the group with negative IVF outcomes.

In females aged >35 from the group with positive IVF outcomes viable embryos were found more frequently and unviable embryos were found less frequently. The nature of chromosomal pathology in study females didn't show a relevant difference among the comparison groups.

Large enough quantity of morphologically healthy but genetically abnormal embryos was also detected. With no PGD an embryologist would undoubtedly choose the embryos that reached the blastocyst phase. And this would lead to a negative IVF outcome.

Along with this, there were also the embryos that were genetically healthy but morphologically defective. All these data suggest that the protocols of controlled ovarian hyperstimulation, used medicinal drugs, embryological phase and procedure of PGD itself need to be improved to obtain a high-quality embryo and positive IVF outcome.

So, while there are contradictory data, the analysis of the world literature data and the results obtained by us in the course of the study revealed great advantages of pre-implantation diagnosis. With its wide diagnostic capabilities, PGD as part of the ART program makes it possible to select and transfer embryos with no chromosomal abnormalities into the uterine cavity, to reduce the risk of miscarriage and multiple pregnancies and to improve the chances of successful implantation and the birth of a healthy child.

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GEOPOLITICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE ANAKLIA DEEP SEA PORT FOR GEORGIA: A NEW STRATEGIC HUB IN EURASIA

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Georgia is a small country in the South Caucasus region. It is bounded to the West by the Black Sea, to the North by Russian Federation. To the South, the country shares borders with Turkey and Armenia and to the Southeast with Azerbaijan. The territory of Georgia is 69.700 square kilometres and the population of the country reaches about 3.78 million (**Georgia country profile, 2019**).

Georgia is situated at strategically important crossroads between Western Asia and Eastern Europe, Black and Caspian Seas; it is positioned along the shortest routes between China and Europe. For this reason, throughout history, the country attracted considerable interest of the world's greatest Empires, such as the Russian, Roman, Ottoman, Mongol and Persian Empires. Georgia was eventually annexed by the Russian Empire in the 19th century. Following the dissolution of the USSR, the country regained independence from the Soviet Union; however civil wars broke out in the country due to the two separatist regions of Abkhazia and South Ossetia.

Following the dissolution of the Soviet Union, Georgia hosts two central pipelines: Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan oil and Baku-Tbilisi-Erzurum gas pipelines which run from the Caspian Sea to Europe, bypassing Georgian territory and transport Caspian hydrocarbon resources to Europe (**Iomia, 2017**). In the twenty-first century, Georgia once again attracted worldwide attention since it represents a critical transport node on the new "One Belt and One Road" project between China and Europe.

According to the Anaklia Development Consortium, Anaklia Port will be the first deep water port of Georgia, and its infrastructure, equipment, and superior customer service will be the main guarantee for the productivity and efficiency of the Anaklia port. Anaklia Deep Sea Port will be designed over the course of 9 phases, with an aggregate investment of \$2.5 billion. Anaklia Port's depth will be 16 meters which enable to berth vessels up to 10,000 TEUs in capacity. Thus, ADC's fundamental objective is to establish Anaklia as a strategic hub for the new Silk Road trade route to and from Central Asia, between China and Europe. The mentioned, on the other hand, brings the country considerable economic growth and stresses Georgia's economic and geopolitical influence in the Black Sea region (**Anaklia Development Consortium, 2020**). However, big powers demonstrate a serious clash of interest to the construction of the Anaklia Deep Sea Port, which in turn, makes it harder to predict the future development of the project.

Construction of Anaklia Sea project has further worsened the U.S.-China relations, which in turn, have already been illustrated in the economic war between Washington and Beijing. As Michael Carpenter, the former assistant deputy secretary of defense and director of the Biden Center stated: "if US investors are forced out of the Anaklia project in favor of Chinese companies, this would send a chill and potentially even freeze future US and Western investments in Georgia" (**Transparency international, 2019**).

On June 11, 2019, in recognition of 10th anniversary of the joint declaration of the U.S.-Georgia strategic partnership, the U.S. Secretary of State Mike Pompeo once again highlighted the significance of the mutual partnership between the two countries and stressed the high significance of Georgia as one of the biggest contributors to global security among the NATO aspirant countries (**U.S. Department of State**). Most importantly, he expressed hope that Georgia would see the [Anaklia] project through to the end. According to Pompeo, Anaklia port would deepen Georgia's relations with free economies and help it to avoid the Russian and Chinese economic influence in the region (**Transparency international, 2019**). The Prime-minister of Georgia, in his turn, underlined the growing economic relations between the two countries and stated that the U.S.-Georgia strategic partnership will eventually lead Georgia "to a unique model of trade cooperation" (**Civil.ge, 2019**).

The People's Republic of China extended official diplomatic recognition to the Republic of Georgia on June 9, 1992. Bilateral ties have advanced gradually in the 25 years since. Cooperation is mostly confined to the economic sphere, focusing on FDI and trade. Bilateral trade has expanded significantly since trade relations were first established in 1992, and especially since 2010, as Georgia's economy recovered from the 2008 August War (**Larsen, 2017: 5**).

According to **Larsen (2017: 4)**

Georgia possesses three key features that make it attractive as a participant in China's Belt and Road initiative (BRI): Free Trade Agreements (FTAs) with both the European Union (EU) and China; an outlet to the Black Sea and overland links with Turkey, which offer platforms from which China can more efficiently conduct trade with the European Union (the second factor augmenting the first); and a flexible position at the fulcrum of two regional formats important for the BRI's success—the Georgia, Ukraine, Azerbaijan, and Moldova (GUAM) group and the Azerbaijan, Georgia, Turkey trilateral group (AGT).

Furthermore, Anaklia Deep Sea Port became "apple of discord" between the U.S. and Russia as well, since the Black Sea and South Caucasus have always been in the special focus of Moscow. Russia has always considered South Caucasus as a "sphere of its influence". The U.S.-Russia clashes of interests have been aggravated since the

enlargement of NATO and the EU in 2004 and 2007 (Spechler, 2007). Kremlin strictly opposed NATO's further expansion which had also been illustrated in Russia's war in Georgia in August 2008. Later, the annexation of Crimea was an explicit demonstration of Moscow to show the rest of the world that it would no more compromise Western presence in the post-Soviet space (Aljazeera.com 2019). However, NATO continues its military exercises in the Black Sea and welcomes Georgia's Euro atlantic aspirations. In this regard, it is significant to note that the development of Anaklia Deep Sea Port is of pivotal importance to enhance Georgia-NATO relations and eccelarate Georgia's integration into the north Atlantic Treaty Organisation.

The U.S. is actively assisting Georgia in strengthening and deepening the Euro-Atlantic ties, building democratic institutions and supporting the country to transfer into the most developed and economically stable partner in the South Caucasus region. Georgia, in turn, is a significant ally of the U.S. in the war on terror and hugely contributes to the U.S. led anti-terrorism operations in Iraq and Afghanistan (Lomia, 2019: 54).

Since the early years of Georgia's independence, the U.S. has fully supported Georgia's democratization process and has tried to maintain stability in the region, thereby increasing the country's opportunities for further economic progress and development. Clear illustration of the above mentioned is the great efforts made by the U.S. President Bill Clinton to construct the Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan (BTC) oil pipeline in the late 1990s, which was of fundamental significance for the stabilization of post-war Georgian economy. The BTC pipeline gave Georgia a new dimension since it has attracted worldwide attention as a major transit corridor in the Caucasus region for energy resources (Ibidem, 61).

The U.S. is supporting the "Anaklia Deep Sea Port project" (the project of a century), which on the other hand, means that Georgia will gain significant worldwide attention as a regional transport and transit hub through the development the historic Silk Road route, which is considered to be the fastest trade routes between China and Europe. As it was mentioned above, "Anaklia" is a project of key significance for the economic development of Georgia. The project will further strengthen the U.S.-Georgia business ties and stands to diminish Russian and Chinese economic influence in Georgia (Ibidem, 62).

It should be emphasized that „creeping annexation" is not only an act of illegal occupation of Georgian territories, Russia, on the one hand, aims at weakening Georgia's economy, and on the other hand, tries to increase the dependence of Georgian export on the Russian market. Furthermore, Russia interferes with Georgia's Euro-Atlantic integration and diminishes the status of the country on an international stage by showing the rest of the world that Georgia is unable to independently carry out its political course without the support of Moscow (Lomia, 2020: 124).

Recently, some of the U.S. senators and congressmen published official letters highlighting their concerns about the Georgian government's close relations with the Kremlin and attempts of expulsing the U.S. companies from the Anaklia port project (Radio Liberty 2020; Glurjidge and Dzamukashvili, 2020.) The mentioned raised concerns about the future strategic partnership between the U.S. and Georgia; however, as it has been highlighted by the high officials of the U.S., Washington still supports Georgia's economic development and political reforms to the way of its democratization and remains the strongest partner of the South Caucasus country.

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AZƏRBAYCANDA ENERJİ EFFEKTİVLİYİNİN YÜKSƏLDİLMƏSİ İSTİQAMƏTLƏRİ

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XÜLASƏ

Enerji effektivliyi fenomeni müasir dünyada yeni reallıq olaraq, bəşəri həyatın bütün sferalarına öz təsirini göstərməkdədir. O, hər bir ölkədə enerji təhlükəsizliyinin təmin olunması və möhkəmləndirilməsində əsas iqtisadi alətlərdən biri olaraq çıxış edir. Bu səbəbdən də həmin ölkələr milli enerji strategiyalarına yenidən baxır, onu global çağırışlara uyğun korrektə edərək təkmilləşdirir. Bu istiqamətdə aparıcı dünya ölkələri, xüsusən də Avropa İttifaqı daha çox fərqlənir. Aparılan təhlillə müəyyən edilmişdir ki, həmin ölkələrdə, həmçinin Avropa İttifaqında reallaşdırılan enerji effektivliyi strategiyasının müsbət nəticələrindən Azərbaycanda da faydalanmaq üçün mühüm əsaslar və tələblər var. Bundan irəli gələrək, məqalədə bu qabaqcıl təcrübənin Azərbaycanda enerji sferasında aparılan islahatlar sistemində də daxil edilməsi vacib şərt olaraq irəli sürülür və bu istiqamətdə müvafiq təkliflər əsaslandırılır.

Açar sözlər: enerji effektivliyi, bərpaolunan enerji, enerji təhlükəsizliyi, enerji menecmenti.

DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN AZERBAIJAN

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ABSTRACT

The phenomenon of energy efficiency, as a new reality in the modern world, affects all spheres of human life. It is one of the main economic tools in ensuring and strengthening energy security in every country. For this reason, these countries are reviewing their national energy strategies and adjusting them to meet global challenges. The leading countries of the world, especially the European Union, are more different in this direction. The analysis revealed that there are important grounds and requirements for Azerbaijan to benefit from the positive results of the energy efficiency strategy implemented in those countries, as well as in the European Union. Therefore, the article states that it is important to include this best practice in the system of reforms in the energy sector in Azerbaijan, and substantiates relevant proposals in this direction.

Keywords: energy efficiency, renewable energy, energy security, energy management.

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ЭТАПЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ МОТИВАЦИИ БУДУЩИХ ПЕДАГОГОВ К ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОМУ САМОСОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЮ

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РЕЗЮМЕ

В тезисах статьи обоснована актуальность и охарактеризованы последовательные этапы формирования у будущих педагогов мотивации профессионального самосовершенствования

Ключевые слова: мотивация, профессиональное самосовершенствование, будущие педагоги

STAGES OF FORMATION OF MOTIVATION OF FUTURE TEACHERS TO PROFESSIONAL SELF-IMPROVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

In the theses of the article, the author substantiates the relevance of the formation of professional self-improvement motivation among future teachers, appealing to the fact that motivation is not only a means that determines the success of a teacher's professional activity and contributes to the realization of his professional goals, but also an important psychological factor that provides professional stability, an appropriate level of professional competence, activates creative search and directs to positive professional transformations.

By professional improvement, the author understands a specific type of professional pedagogical activity; a conscious, purposeful process of increasing the level of professional competence and developing professional qualities in accordance with external social requirements, professional activity conditions and personal development program.

Motivation for professional self-improvement is presented as a combination of three components: an adequate self-assessment of their own capabilities, awareness of the need for self-improvement and consideration of the requirements that modern society imposes on teachers.

The conducted research allowed the author to identify and characterize three consecutive stages of the process of formation of professional self-improvement motivation in future teachers: preparatory, practical and final. Each stage has its own specific goal, using specific organizational forms and methods. The transition from one stage to another is conditional and is characterized by quantitative and qualitative changes in the structure of students' personality, their system of values and behavioral reactions.

In conclusion, the author concludes that it is necessary to study and implement in the educational process the conditions that ensure the effectiveness of the gradual formation of professional self-improvement motivation among future teachers: creating positive motivational attitudes among students; forming a system of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for self-improvement; creating a favorable socio-psychological atmosphere for the manifestation of activity, creativity and personal growth of students; updating the need for self-improvement.

Keywords: motivation, professional self-improvement, future teachers.

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МЕТОДИКА ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ДИСЦИПЛИНЫ «ОСНОВЫ ВОЖАТСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ» ОБУЧАЮЩИМСЯ ГУМАНИТАРНЫХ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОСТЕЙ

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РЕЗЮМЕ

В тезисах статьи раскрыта методика преподавания дисциплины «Основы вожатской деятельности» обучающимся гуманитарных специальностей, которая охватывает комплекс эффективных форм, методов и средств обучения.

Ключевые слова: методика, вожатская деятельность, профессиональный стандарт.

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING THE DISCIPLINE "BASICS OF DRIVING ACTIVITIES" TO STUDENTS OF HUMANITARIAN SPECIALTIES

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ABSTRACT

The abstracts of the article reveal the methodology of teaching the discipline "Fundamentals of counselor activity" to students of humanitarian specialties, which covers a complex of effective forms, methods and means of teaching.

Keywords: methodology, counselor activity, professional standard.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОГО ПРОЕКТИРОВАНИЯ В УЧЕБНО-ВОСПИТАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ

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РЕЗЮМЕ

В статье представлена специфика применения проектных педагогических технологий в учебно-воспитательном процессе образовательной организации, описаны ключевые компетенции обучающихся, овладению которыми способствует проектная технология, представлены преимущества использования проектных технологий в образовательной организации, а также описаны особенности подготовки бакалавров направления подготовки 44.03.02 «Психолого-педагогическое образование» в аспекте овладения ими проектными педагогическими технологиями.

Ключевые слова: проектирование, педагогическое проектирование, педагогические технологии.

FEATURES OF USING THE TECHNOLOGY OF PEDAGOGICAL DESIGN IN THE TEACHING AND EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The article presents the specifics of the application of design of pedagogical technologies in educational process of educational institutions, describes the key competencies, the mastery of which contributes to project technology, presented the advantages of using project technology in educational organizations, and describes the features of training of bachelors in the field of 44.03.02 "Psycho-pedagogical education" in the aspect of mastering their project teaching technologies.

Project technology is an effective tool for acquiring new knowledge, skills and values necessary for personal development. It has taken an important place in the educational process of modern schools and is implemented during regular, extracurricular work. Project technology helps students master five key competencies that are key to the twenty-first century: 1) political and social competencies, such as the ability to take responsibility, manage conflicts in a non-violent way, participate in joint decision-making and in the functioning and improvement of democratic institutions; 2) competencies related to life in a multicultural society, such as awareness of the diversity and diversity of this world, respect, tolerance, culture of peace, and the ability to live with people of other cultures, languages, and religions; 3) communication competencies; 4) competencies related to the challenges of the information society; 5) the ability to learn throughout life as a basis for continuous training in professional terms, as well as in personal and public life.

Project technologies are characterized by a wide range of advantages: simultaneous combination of individual and collective activities, the possibility of self-realization, globalization of the educational process, vision of a specific result; team work (performing certain roles: Manager, performer, partner, consultant, adviser, statistician); implementation of age-related needs for independent, practical and creative activities (initiative, self-elimination of obstacles, development of talents and aptitudes, making extraordinary decisions); assessment of the results and social significance of activities; the possibility of using modern technologies and the Internet in the process of working on the project by both teachers and students, the use of various forms of interaction, including interactive ones, which allows implementing the pedagogy of cooperation.

The relevance of the use of pedagogical project technology in the educational process of an educational organization makes it necessary to introduce into the curricula of the training direction 44.03.02 relevant disciplines aimed at forming the foundations of project culture in future specialists in the field of education.

So, in the Evpatoria Institute of Social Sciences (branch) V. I. Vernadsky Federal state University, in the curriculum of bachelor's training in the direction of training 44.03.02 "Psychological and pedagogical education", as part of the study of the discipline "Social and pedagogical design", students develop such universal, general professional and professional competencies: UC-2 – is able to determine the range of tasks within the set goal and choose the best ways to solve them, based on current legal norms, available resources and restrictions; GP-2-is able to participate in the development of basic and additional educational programs, develop their individual components (including using ICT); PC-3 – is able to provide organizational and pedagogical support for the educational process.

As a result of studying the discipline "Social and pedagogical design", the student must: know: methods for presenting and describing the results of project activities; features of basic and additional educational programs; approximate content of extracurricular activities in sports, social, spiritual and moral, general intellectual, general cultural areas; be able to: design a solution to a specific project task, choosing the best way to solve it, based on current legal norms and available resources and restrictions; use knowledge of features of basic and additional educational programs in professional activities; develop a program of extracurricular activities in accordance with the requirements of the educational standart; to possess: basics of developing project specifications; skills in analysis of primary and secondary education programmes; skills development programmes extracurricular activities in one of the areas of educational standart: sports, social, spiritual and moral, all-intellectual, cultural. In the course of studying the discipline, such educational technologies as interactive lectures, group discussions, role-playing games, trainings, situation analysis and simulation models are used

Keywords: methodology, guidance, professional standard.

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ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНАЯ СРЕДА КАК ФАКТОР СОЦИАЛИЗАЦИИ ЛИЧНОСТИ ПОДРОСТКОВ

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РЕЗЮМЕ

В данной статье изучена сущность процесса социализации, описана специфика проявления процесса социализации в подростковом возрасте; выделены уровни социализации подростков; определена роль образовательной среды как фактора социализации личности подростков, описаны принципы проектирования безопасной образовательной среды с целью успешной социализации подростков.

Ключевые слова: социализация, подростки, уровни социализации, среда, образовательная среда, проектирование.

THE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT AS A FACTOR OF SOCIALIZATION OF THE PERSONALITY OF TEENAGERS

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ABSTRACT

This article studies the essence of the process of socialization, describes the specificity of the manifestation of the process of socialization in adolescence; highlighted the levels of socialization of adolescents; the role of the educational environment as a factor in the socialization of the personality of adolescents is determined, the principles of designing a safe educational environment for the purpose of successful socialization of adolescents are described.

Keywords: socialization, adolescents, levels of socialization, environment, educational environment, design.

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ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ АКТИВНЫХ ФОРМ ПРОВЕДЕНИЯ ПРАКТИЧЕСКИХ ЗАНЯТИЙ ПРИ ИЗУЧЕНИИ ДИСЦИПЛИНЫ «ПСИХОЛОГО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЕ КОНСУЛЬТИРОВАНИЕ И КОРРЕКЦИЯ В ОБРАЗОВАНИИ» ДЛЯ ПОДГОТОВКИ МАГИСТРОВ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ПОДГОТОВКИ 44.04.02 ПСИХОЛОГО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ

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РЕЗЮМЕ

Статья посвящена характеристике активных форм обучения магистров направления подготовки 44.04.02 «Психолого-педагогическое образование» на материалах дисциплины «Психолого-педагогическое консультирование и коррекция в образовании». Автор обращает внимание на эффективность использования имитационных и неимитационных активных методов при изучении дисциплины. В статье рассмотрено влияние данных форм работы на развитие творческого потенциала и активности магистров, стимулирование исследовательского поиска и закрепление имеющихся знаний.

Ключевые слова: активные формы обучения, имитационные, неимитационные методы, консультирование и коррекция, магистры.

THE USE OF ACTIVE FORMS OF CONDUCTING PRACTICAL LESSONS WHEN STUDYING THE DISCIPLINE "PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL COUNSELING AND CORRECTION IN EDUCATION" FOR TRAINING MASTERS OF PREPARATORY PREPARATORY PREPARATION 44.04.02

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the characteristics of active forms of training for masters of the training direction 44.04.02 "Psychological and pedagogical education" on the materials of the discipline "Psychological and pedagogical counseling and correction in education". The author draws attention to the effectiveness of the use of imitative and non-imitative active methods in the study of the discipline. The article examines the influence of these forms of work on the development of the creative potential and activity of masters, stimulating research and consolidation of existing knowledge.

Keywords: active forms of education, imitation, non-imitation methods, counseling and correction, masters.

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ТЪЮТОРСТВО КАК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДДЕРЖКИ

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ABSTRACT

In the theses of the article, the concepts of "tutor", "tutoring", "tutor support" are considered. The functions of a tutor as a teacher are disclosed. Tutor support of a student of an educational organization and technology of pedagogical support are correlated.

Keywords: tutor, tutoring, pedagogical support.

РЕЗЮМЕ

В тезисах статьи рассмотрены понятия «тьютор», «тьюторство», «тьюторское сопровождение». Раскрыты функции тьютора как педагога. Соотнесено тьюторское сопровождение обучающегося образовательной организации и технологии педагогической поддержки.

Ключевые слова: тьютор, тьюторство, педагогическая поддержка.

TUTORING AS A TECHNOLOGY OF PEDAGOGICAL SUPPORT

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ABSTRACT

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Keywords: tutor, tutoring, pedagogical support.

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AZƏRBAYCANIN ELEKTROENERGETİKA SEKTORUNDA İNKİŞAFIN BAŞLICA HƏDƏFLƏRİ

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XÜLASƏ

Müasir qlobal iqtisadiyyatın tərəqqisində elektroenergetika əhəmiyyətini artırmaqda və aparıcı rolunu saxlamaqdadır. Hər il bu istiqamətdə istehlak tələbləri artır, dövriyyəyə yeni generasiya gücləri daxil olur. Azərbaycan Respublikasında da bu sahənin inkişafına xüsusi diqqət yetirilir. Həyata keçirilən enerji siyasəti və görülməli tədbirlər nəticəsində ölkədə elektroenerji təhlükəsizliyi tam təmin olunmuş, Azərbaycan bu sahədə də ixracatçı ölkəyə çevrilərək, elektrik enerjisinin əlçatanlıq əmsalına görə dünyada ikinci yerdə qərarlaşmışdır. Hazırda bu sektorda aparılan islahatlar dərinləşərək yeni təkmil mərhələyə daxil olur, əhalinin elektrik enerjisi ilə təchizatı davamlı yaxşılaşdırılır, iqtisadiyyatın inkişafının və milli enerji təhlükəsizliyinin təminatı daha da möhkəmləndirilir. Elmi aktualıq kəsb edən bütün bu məsələlər təhlili və qiymətləndirmələr əsasında məqalə tədqiqatının da ana xəttini təşkil edir. Yerində yetirilən təhlillər əsasında məqalədə Azərbaycanın elektroenergetika sektorunda inkişafın başlıca hədəflərini genişləndirən yeni istiqamətlər təqdim olunur.

Açar sözlər: elektroenergetika təhlükəsizliyi, nüvə energetikası, bərpaolunan enerji, enerji effektivliyi.

THE MAIN GOALS OF DEVELOPMENT IN THE ELECTROENERGETIC SECTOR OF AZERBAIJAN

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ABSTRACT

In the development of the modern global economy, the electric power industry is increasing its important role and continues to play a leading role. Every year, consumer demands in this direction are growing, and new generating capacities are being put into circulation. Special attention is paid to the development of this sphere in the Republic of Azerbaijan. As a result of the energy policy implemented and the measures taken, the country's electricity security has been fully ensured, and Azerbaijan has become an export-oriented country in this area and is ranked second in the world for the electricity accessibility ratio. The reforms carried out in this sector are deepening and entering a new stage of development, the supply of electricity to the population is steadily improving, development of the economy and national energy security are further strengthened. All these issues of scientific actuality form the main line of Article research on the basis of reviews and evaluations. On the basis of the analysis, the article presents new directions expanding the main targets of development in the electroenergetic sector of Azerbaijan.

Keywords: electricity security, nuclear energy, renewable energy, energy efficiency.

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